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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>TOSHE - Test Of Systems for Harsh Environment</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA02-13</i>
General application	<i>Space, high-reliability applications, SoC/FPGA characterization</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Luigi DILILLO, LIRMM - University of Montpellier - CNRS</i>
Date of the experiment	<i>28/06/2022</i>
Facility	<i>PARTREC</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>12 hours</i>

Objectives of the experiments

This proposal focuses on the evaluation of Single Event Effects (SEE) in COTS (Commercial Off-The-Shelf) devices and SoCs (System-on-Chip). COTS products are becoming of interest for many space applications, as they offer much higher performance, lower power consumption and lower cost than the few available radiation-hardened counterparts. This proposal supports WP6-JR2 “Standardization of system level radiation qualification methodology”, in RADNEXT project, which specifically addresses system-level radiation testing. Goals of this project is to develop methodologies to enhance observability of complex systems, remote testing, research of environmental conditions to achieve best experimental success, data collection and process and represent an extension of the studies made within RADSAGA project. In this context, the submitters intend to test several complex systems at two different levels:

- Complex devices: PseudoStatic Memory that supports Artificial Intelligence applications (image recognition, Hyperspectral image treatment).
- Characterization of parts of the SoC such as XADC converters. A major common point among most of the experimental setups is the use of the Xilinx Zynq 7000 SoC platform as target or controlling circuit.

The granted beam time was equally split into two WP6-JR2 institutions: UM/LIRMM and DLR. To provide more appealing results in the first targeted topic, UM/LIRMM changed the focus of the

PseudoStatic memory test to a broader characterization of a processor-based system targeting space applications and has envisioned utilization for artificial intelligence applications.

Experiment test report

This report provides a summary of each experiment and presents some preliminary results. The topics are segmented concerning each experiment leading institution. Also, general information about the test facility is provided.

The experiment was conducted in the AGOR beamline, part of the KVI, at the University of Groningen, NL. It generates high-energy protons with fluxes reaching $2 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ for energies up to 190 MeV.

1. University of Montpellier (UM) – LIRMM

For the characterization of the HARV-SoC, we proposed and implemented a strategy targeting enhanced fault tracking in a fault-tolerant RISC-V SoC by extending the fault observability of the SoC implementation through runtime fault detection. For this purpose, we monitor critical structures of the SoC architecture to report relevant information about the faults triggered by the radiation-induced events. This solution allows a better understanding of the underlying impacts of faults in the SoC design compared to alternative strategies. Furthermore, it enables more efficient use of the hardening countermeasures and provides the means for the *application* to perform recovery actions in case of critical failures. To implement and validate the concept, we instrument the RISC-V SoC with this solution and evaluate the observability effectiveness through a neutron irradiation campaign.

The solution for providing fault observation consists of implementing an event handler component in the processor core that requests traps when events are detected. It monitors the signals from the fault-tolerant structures, saving relevant information about the detected events, as presented in Fig. 1.1. The trap controller handles the request as an exception, ensuring that the processor will handle this event as soon as possible. The detectable events in the event handler include the following events of the processor: Program Counter (PC) single- and double-bit upsets, Instruction Register (IR) single- and double-bit upsets, register file single- and double-bit upsets, control TMR error, and ALU TMR error.

Fig. 1.1. Event handler implementation.

The event handler has a set of registers that store information upon detecting an event. These registers are implemented in the event handler component and are mapped in the memory. This way, we save the data when the event is detected and provide additional information regarding the event details. The basic event information comprises the event identifier, a register in which each bit corresponds to one type of event. The application must clear this register to indicate that the event has been handled, and the execution should continue. Besides that, the event handler also saves the application context information, which comprises the addresses of the instructions that made function calls, up to the point where the event was identified.

Experiment

The experimental configuration consisted of a system-level evaluation setup, using twelve Microchip's M2S010-VFG400 devices. These devices were selected due to their flash-based configuration memory. Serial connections with RS482 protocol were used to transmit the logs generated in the systems under test to a host computer outside the irradiation room. The power supply for the boards was supplied from the control room, which was monitored by current sensors to avoid damages due to SELs (Single-Event Latch-ups).

Each FPGA hosted a RISC-V SoC with observability enabled running different benchmarks combined with different configurations and behavior. The benchmarks applied in these experiments were Coremark and Embench. The Coremark benchmark was configured to 100 iterations, while Embench considers a single execution as 5 cycles of the 17 algorithms of the Embench's set of algorithms. Furthermore, there were two execution behaviors: single executions and endurance. The single execution runs the benchmark once and resets the processor to restart the execution. The endurance behavior executes the benchmark in an infinite loop, stopping only if a critical error is found (i.e., benchmark check operations failure), and in this case, it will execute the benchmark one last time and reset the processor execution. Another parameter for the experiment is the HARV-SoC hardening configurations, which configures the enabling of fault tolerance capabilities for the system. The tested configurations are Hardened, for fault tolerance enabled, Unhardened for fault tolerance disabled, and Switching, which switches between Hardened and Unhardened configurations for each execution, based on the reset cause. Table 1.1 presents the parameters for the experiment executed in each DUT.

Table 1.1 – HARV-SoC Experiments

Board ID	Benchmark algorithm	Execution behavior	Hardening configuration
b0	Coremark	Endurance	Hardened
b1	Embench	Single execution	Switching
b2	Coremark	Single execution	Switching
b3	Coremark	Single execution	Switching
b4	Embench	Single execution	Switching
b5	Coremark	Endurance	Unhardened
b6	Coremark	Single execution	Switching
b7	Embench	Single execution	Switching
b8	Embench	Endurance	Hardened

b9	Embench	Endurance	Unhardened
b10	Embench	Endurance	Hardened
b11	Embench	Endurance	Unhardened

For the experiment execution, we selected the highest energy available at the facility (184 MeV) and tested different fluxes for the experiments. The tested fluxes varied from 1×10^6 to 2×10^8 $p/cm^2/s$. It is worth noting that most fluxes were used as calibration for selecting the optimal flux for our experiments, in which we noticed that fluxes lower than 1×10^7 $p/cm^2/s$ have shown a low number of events. Therefore, the fluxes selected for the experiment were 4×10^7 $p/cm^2/s$, 1×10^8 $p/cm^2/s$, and 2×10^8 $p/cm^2/s$.

As a result, we obtained several different events in the HARV processor core and SoC, shown in Table 1.2 and Table 1.3, respectively. In the processor core, we obtained a total of 40 events, most due to single-bit upsets in the register file, which had 27 events. For the SoC, the implemented observability could identify a total of 247 events, where most of them were single-bit upsets in the external SDRAM, which was being used as a data memory for the program.

Throughout the test campaign, no events were detected in more than 99% of the executions, and the benchmark execution ran perfectly. We noticed that, compared to previous test campaigns, the events show that our implementation was able to mitigate most of the load access faults by implementing the peripheral reset when a load access timeout event is detected, which has been able to recover faulty states of the peripherals, enabling the application to continue its execution.

Therefore, using the implemented fault tolerance techniques has improved the reliability of the processor and SoC, while the event handler was able to provide awareness for the processor and software application by reporting the detected events, which allows the application to handle the fault events according to its requirements.

Table 1.2 – Events in HARV processor core

Event	b0	b1	b2	b3	b4	b5	b6	b7	b8	b9	b10	b11	Total
program counter single-bit upset		1		1		1			2	1			6
program counter double-bit upset								1	1				2
instruction register single-bit upset													
instruction register double-bit upset		1	2										3
register file single-bit upset	3		3	2	7	5	1	6	6	2	3	3	27
register file double-bit upset						1							1

control TMR error													
ALU TMR error		1											1

Table 1.3 – SoC events

Event	b0	b1	b2	b3	b4	b5	b6	b7	b8	b9	b10	b11	Total
CRC error	0	18	1	10	3	5	1	8	3		2		51
load access fault		1											1
store access fault													
load access timeout	3	20	3	7	5	6	4	4	1	4	3	7	67
store access timeout													
memory single-bit upset	12	4	11	17	12	9	10	14	7	11	7	4	118
memory double-bit upset			1	2				1		2	1		10

2. German Aerospace Center (DLR)

This experiment aims on the further evaluation of the Xilinx Zynq-7000 System-on-Chip (SoC). The Zynq has been already characterized by multiple institution under different radiation conditions including total ionizing dose (TID) and single event effects (SEE) by any kind of particle (Neutrons, Protons and Heavy-Ions). For this experiment the scientist in charge are focusing on specific functions of the Zynq under particle irradiation and their response as well as the investigation of soft error mitigation techniques.

Objectives and Goals

Susceptibility of Zynq XADC

The Zynq SoC consist of a 16-channel integrated analog-to-digital converter (ADC) module using two 12-bit 1 MPSPS ADCs, not yet treated in literature. Considering the XADC as an integrated current monitoring tool, systems may simplify in hardware by implementing current sense mechanism to observe single event latchup (SEL). Thus, the susceptibility of the Zynq XADC to SEEs is of interest to validate their use as SEL monitor. In the following the key objectives of this experiments are listed:

- Sample the current values of the GSDR XADC with a sample rate of 100Hz
- Capture RAW ADC Data and convert the data to analog/voltage values during post processing.
- Capture the voltage and current values of the GSDR with the Labjack
- Compare data to investigate SEEs in the XADC Data

- SEE vs. Energy should be investigated (a minimum of 30 Errors per run shall be observed, the flux shall be in accordance to the requirements of the SEM IP Core tests)

Evaluation of the SEM-IP Core

The open available soft error mitigation (SEM) IP Core for the Xilinx 7000 series is a powerful and commonly used tool for the fault injection, detection and potentially correction of single event upsets (SEU) in the FPGA configuration [4]. Minor publications are available for the use of the SEM IP Core on the Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC. The SEM IP-Core supports several interfaces, including an AXI-interface to access the status and control the IP core out of a running OS, a dedicated UART interface as well as logic outputs. For this experiment, we propose the evaluation of the SEM IP with respect to its SEE response on the UART interface and its logical outs. In the following the key objectives of this experiments are listed:

- Failure (correctable and uncorrectable vs. Energy with a fix flux)
- SEM IP Core vs. CRAM readback
 - If an uncorrectable error occurs or the SEM does not work properly read back the CRAM
 - Save the data and then continue the radiation with the same selected flux until further $1E+7$ p/cm² are achieved.
 - The read back again the CRAM and save the data (to compare the SEM IP Core failures detected/corrected and the numbers of error in the CRAM logic without SEM IP Core active)
 - Make a separation of SEU in the complete CRAM logic and MBUs (multiple cells flipped in a frame)
- Failure vs. Flux (fix energy, variable flux (max. $1E+9$)
 - Select a fix energy that causes a moderate to high amount of events
 - Select a low, medium and high flux and evaluate the SEM IP Core behavior vs. flux. (in terms of correctable and uncorrectable)
- SEM IP Core failure vs. CRAM capacity
 - See SEM IP Core behavior with complex FPGA design
 - SEM IP Core with minimalistic FPGA Design
 - Fix Energy and Fix Flux.

System under Test

Description

The test vehicle (Figure 2.1) is a software-defined radio (SDR) platform developed by the DLR that already has been tested under proton irradiation at KVI and the mixed-field radiation test facility of CHARM [1]. The primary target of the test vehicle is the Zynq-7020 System on Chip that is being studied in this test campaign. Beside the Zynq, the GSDR also consist of DDR3 SDRAM, NAND flashes and specific RFIC technologies that are used to enable radio operations.

Technology Information

The Xilinx Zynq-7020 SoC is based on a 28nm CMOS process.

Table 2.1 - Sample Information

Sample ID	Device Number	Product SN	Date Code	LOT Code	Fabrication-Info
1	Xilinx XC7020	CLG484ABX1813	D5590269A	1813	28nm CMOS, Taiwan

Figure 2.1- SDR test object, top: without RF board, bottom: fully assembled SDR.

Figure 2.2 - Xilinx Zynq DUT on GSDR

Figure 2.3 - Sample information

Test setup

The test setup for this test is presented in the following Figure 2.4. The test equipment consists of the following part:

- PC: Computer to control the SUT and monitor parameters
- RS422 Converter: To allow access between the PC and the SUT
- Ethernet Hub: To allow access to the test setup to any computer
- Power Supply: To support the SUT with +5VDC
- LabJack: To measure parameters of the SUT
- USB-JTAG interface

Figure 2.4 - Test setup schematic

Test Procedure

- General requirements before ending run with certain energy:
 - Target fluence of 1E+11 is achieved
 - More than 30 SEM or XADC/CPU critical errors occurred
 - Potentially increase target fluence to improve statistical analysis if time allows
- Objectives are (see also chapter 2):
 - XADC Failure vs. Energy: Test at three to four different energies (no flux dependencies)
 - SEM Failure vs. Energy: Test at three to four different energies (flux dependencies)
 - Failure vs. Flux: For SEM IP Core, three different fluxes shall be selected (min, medium, max).
 - Failure vs. Capacity: For SEM IP Core: CRAM capacity dependency (for Fix Energy and Flux)

Figure 2.5 - Test procedures flowchart

Test Results

XADC

The XADC was supervised by regular queries of the measured sensor data at a rate of 100 Hz. Due to the XADC being embedded inside the SoC, it was not possible to apply a static reference voltage

to all XADC pins. Instead, each of the XADC channels had to be sampled at normal device operation with the voltage data that was currently present at each channel input.

The measured data of every XADC channel was surveilled for any significant data glitches that imply a potential single event effect, or a full failure of the XADC. A full failure, however, did not occur, neither softly nor permanently.

Because the measurements had to be performed during regular device operation, the data of the supervised voltages and currents shows a significant amount of noise contributing to an overall high variance, even without irradiation. Data glitches due to potential single event effects were therefore only considered as such potential events if the outliers are:

- above or below 99.99 percent of all other samples,
- only single-sample outliers, as these are the only outliers a single event caused.

To further mitigate the uncertainties caused by the highly variant data, each run and each XADC channel is compared between irradiation (beam-on) and no irradiation (beam-off).

Because the XADC device delivers MSB-aligned 12-bit values (MSB-aligned 16 bit samples), one can expect at least some single event effects to create bit-flips in the higher bits, that, if occurring, should be clearly visible in the data.

Figure 2.6 shows the number of singular outliers outside the confidence of 99.99% for each run and each XADC channel. Figure 2.7, certain channels (I_VCC1V0 and VCCPDRO) are left out for better visibility.

Beam conditions for individual runs:

Run1: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $1\text{E}+7$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $1\text{E}+10$ #/cm²

Run2: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $5\text{E}+7$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $1.65\text{E}+10$ #/cm²

Run3: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $5\text{E}+6$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $5.88\text{E}+9$ #/cm²

Run4: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $5\text{E}+6$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $3.41\text{E}+9$ #/cm²

Run5: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $1\text{E}+7$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $7.01\text{E}+9$ #/cm²

Run6: Energy: 184 MeV; Flux: $5\text{E}+7$ #/cm²/s; Fluence: $1.52\text{E}+10$ #/cm²

Figure 2.6 - XADC data: Singular outliers outside of 99.99% confidence interval

Figure 2.7 - XADC data: Singular outliers outside of 99.99% confidence interval

First of all, during the entire test campaign, the XADC did not show any critical functional failure nor it received permanent damage. Furthermore, looking at the overall results presented in Figure 2.6 and Figure 2.7, there is no clear indication of an increased occurrence of outliers during beam-on compared to beam-off. For Run 3 and Run 4, this can be assumed at first, because all channels show more outliers compared to beam-off time. However, looking at the fluence for each run, Run 3 and Run 4 were actually done at lower fluence than for example Run 1 and Run 2, so this connection cannot be made. Selected channels appear to show strong deviations, for example Run 3 Channel I_VCC1V8_CORE. It is worth looking at these and others in detail to get a clearer picture. For

I_VCC1V8_CORE (Figure 2.8), the detected outliers belong to a unique dip in this very channel and this very run.

Figure 2.8 - XADC Run 3 channel I_VCC1V8_CORE

Apart from this, there were no other anomalies observed that could not be explained with certainty, and this anomaly cannot be attributed to a radiation induced single event effect. Apart from this anomaly, all remaining runs and data curves showed no unclear events, and, most importantly, none indicate SEU specific behavior.

It is nevertheless worth looking at these selected figures to understand why no SEU have been observed and what other factors contributed to the data variance and outliers that appear in Figure 2.6 and Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.9 - Run 2 channel I_VCC1V0

Figure 2.9 shows XADC data of the current sensor for the main power input. The dips in the data belong to RAM readouts of the SEM IP core for the second experiment of this test campaign, and are therefore of purely functional nature. The power cycles and beam-cycles were also performed for that experiment. The power cycles have another side-effect because, after each power-cycle, the XADC calibrates for offset-correction [1] and ends up with a slightly different base value. This is visible in the stepped curve in Figure 2.10.

It is visible here that the calibration after each power cycle caused noticeable shifts in amplitude. Still, no significant outliers outside of the regular noise can be observed here either.

Figure 2.10 - Run 2 channel I_RF1_VCC1V3-B

Figure 2.11 and Figure 2.12 are other examples of strongly fluctuating data with outliers outside the applied confidence interval that can be associated to the dynamics of the system, rather than to radiation effects.

Figure 2.11 - XADC Run 6 channel I_VCC3V3_PER

Figure 2.12 - Run 5 channel VCCINT

SEM-IP Core

Two different FPGA designs had been tested to check for an impact on the SEM cores functionality. When comparing the error rate between the two designs, only a minor difference can be observed, well within the error margin, as indicated in Figure 2.13. In the following analysis, the designs are ignored, by combining the runs. Therefore, only the beam flux varies. Comparison of the error rate in the first phase, supervised by SEM core, with the second phase, where errors are detected using a JTAG readback. The cross-section is depicted in Figure 2.14. Calculation in the first phase is done by counting the error addresses, divided by the duration of the beam time. By counting addresses instead of error events, the count of flipped bits is calculated correctly in the case of 2-bit errors. In the second phase, the count of differences in the JTAG readback is divided by the beam duration.

Figure 2.13 - Comparison of SEM error rate per design

Figure 2.14 - Comparison of SEM and JTAG over flux rate

The SEM controller prints information on the serial port when detecting and correcting errors. Types of errors in the SEM controller output are (as of PG036, pg. 67 ff):

- "CRC" - non-correctable errors
- "DED" - 2 bit ECC error
- "SED OK" - 1 bit ECC errors

Both DED and SED OK errors are correctable by the SEM controller. Non-correctable CRC errors occur only once per run, because the SEM controller halts after its detection.

Table 2.2: Summary of flux-dependent error observations

Flux	Run count	CRC #/s	DED #/s	SED OK #/s
5.0e7	21	0.06	0.32	4.85
1.0e7	12	0.01	0.07	1.05
0.5e7	13	0.01	0.04	0.49

The SEM core provides the error location for the correctable errors, addressed by frame, word and bit location. For 2-bit errors, both addresses are provided. They indicate a direct physical proximity, with the difference being exactly 1 for all monitored occurrences. When comparing the ratio of 1-bit and 2-bit errors, only 6% to 9% of errors are 2-bit.

Figure 2.15 - Percentage of 1-bit Errors over flux

By adding timestamps to the output lines of the SEM core, we are able to calculate the time needed to handle an error. The timespan includes the time between the state changes to correction (SC 04) until the state changes to observation (SC 02) as presented in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Type of errors and the durations until occurrence

Type	Duration [s]
SED OK (1-bit)	0.009±0.008
DED (2-bit)	0.117±1.09
all	0.015±0.263

Event cross section is calculated by dividing the count of SEM events by the particle fluence. The fluence is calculated by multiplying the mean flux with the run duration (Figure 2-16).

Figure 2.16 - SEM event cross-section over flux

The fatal cross section is calculated by dividing the count of fatal errors by the particle fluence. The fatal error count equals the number of runs, as all runs end in a fatal error. The fluence is calculated by multiplying the mean flux with the run duration (Figure 2-17).

Figure 2.17 - Fatal SEM cross-section over Flux

Discussion

XADC

In short, looking at the results, the XADC did not show erroneous behavior in terms of single event upsets and neither did it fail completely. The data delivered no clear indication of single event effects that affect the device in a way that one would observe data glitches outside of the mean and variance of the measured sensor data.

The evaluations of the XADC data were challenging due to the execution in a dynamic complete system of the carrying SDR platform. Especially the re-initialization and calibration procedures of the XADC between power cycles [1] caused unnecessarily high data variance. However, by comparing outliers between beam-on and beam-off time, it was still possible to conclude with high certainty that no single event effects occurred, at least none that were outside the normal data variance, and hence disruptive in any sense.

Most importantly, as already discussed above, despite being 16-bit wide samples, none of the received data showed any signs of upsets in the MSB area of the samples. These upsets are by far the most easily recognizable ones in the collected data, even in a dynamic running system as this one, it can safely be assumed that no significant SEUs took place.

Post-test analysis of the documentation of the XADC [Control Registers • 7 Series FPGAs and Zynq-7000 SoC XADC Dual 12-Bit 1 MSPS Analog-to-Digital Converter User Guide (UG480) • Reader • Documentation Portal (xilinx.com)] revealed that the XADC also performs averaging by default over 16 sample-sets. Thus, even though that a SEU will occur it is quite likely that those will not be recognized, unless in case of MBU.

It will certainly be necessary and interesting to undertake finer differentiations when looking for outliers in the data, for example by calculating deviations per power cycle and not only per run, to reduce the calibration errors specifically.

Overall, from the results achieved, the XADC can be characterized as very robust towards single event effects under the proton irradiation performed at the PARTREC lab. This is valuable information

for any engineer looking to make use of the XADC for system health supervision and fault detection in a space application.

SEM-IP

When comparing different design sizes, no relevant difference in event rates could be observed. Due to the missing support of binary mask for essential bit classification, that had to be expected. Without access to the essential bit mask, the SEM core has no means to check whether a bit is actually used by the current design. Therefore, it needs to check all memory frames, regardless of its occupation.

The SEM core is able to detect errors at all used fluxes and the error rates are comparable to those of the JTAG reference run. Because of the delay between fatal SEM error and manual beam stop, we were not able to proof the absence of errors aside the recognized ones, as further errors happen after the SEM core halt.

The statistics about error types (1-bit or 2-bit) shows that over 90% of errors are 1-bit error. The ratio might change towards 2-bit errors with higher beam flux, but the error margin is quite high in this analysis.

The correction of 2-bit errors takes about 13 times longer than for 1-bit errors. Because the core is unable to handle other errors in parallel, a rise of 2-bit errors could have an impact on the maximum error rate.

Conclusion

The test shows interesting results for both investigations, the XADC behavior under proton irradiation as well as for the SEM-IP core. The XADC test data show no SEUs nor destructive events on the test board. Due to the fact that the XADC is used on the test vehicle (GSDR) there are some constraints in terms of current measurements, and deviations in the values are expected. We observed that the values are rather small for the ADC and mostly constant. One issue is that the XADC performs a calibration each time the board is booted and the application is executed. Thus, there are multiple steps in between the test data recorded. Moreover, the XADC performs a specific processing that generates an average of 16 sample-sets of the data, where SEUs in mid-range of the ADCs might not be monitored. Thus, an additional test, with setup modification in the settings of the XADCs needs to be applied.

The SEM-IP Core shows expected responses to SEEs as presented in section 5.2. and discussed in section 6.2. Here further analysis of the data is of interest to investigate the distributions of SEUs in the CRAM over the FPGA area. Here, specific decoders have been developed and also being used.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

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As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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